

GOALS AND OBJECTIVES OF THE SUBJECT “ENGINEERING AND COMPUTER GRAPHICS.” INTRODUCTION TO AUTOMATED DESIGN SYSTEMS AND THE AUTOCAD GRAPHIC PROGRAM

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Abstract: This article highlights the goals and objectives of the subject “Engineering and Computer Graphics,” automated design systems, and the significance of the AutoCAD graphic program in the educational process. The study analyzes the development of students’ spatial imagination, technical thinking, and professional-creative competencies through the application of modern CAD technologies in teaching engineering graphics. In addition, the 2D and 3D modeling capabilities of the AutoCAD program, as well as its practical importance in the engineering design process, are scientifically substantiated.

Keywords: Engineering and Computer Graphics, AutoCAD, CAD technologies, automated design system, 2D modeling, 3D modeling, technical drawing, spatial imagination, professional-creative competence, digital technologies.

Introduction. In the era of rapid development of digital technologies, teaching the subject of Engineering and Computer Graphics through modern software tools has become highly significant. In particular, the AutoCAD graphic program is considered an effective tool for creating technical drawings accurately, quickly, and with high quality. This topic highlights the goals and objectives of the subject “Engineering and Computer Graphics,” automated design systems, as well as the role and practical capabilities of the AutoCAD program in the field of engineering.

In today’s rapidly developing environment, work and design processes in the fields of construction, architecture, manufacturing, land reclamation, and agriculture are being carried out on the basis of digital technologies (computer-based systems). Therefore, the subject “Engineering and Computer Graphics” in universities and institutes serves as an important factor in developing the graphical abilities of engineering specialists.

When examining the origin and history of this discipline, it is evident from numerous sources that the great French scientist Gaspard Monge (1746–1818) is regarded as the founder of engineering graphics. He developed the theory of descriptive geometry, created methods for representing objects on two projection planes, and established the scientific foundations of technical drawing. Modern engineering drawing has evolved primarily on the basis of Monge’s methods.

Leonardo da Vinci (1452–1519), known worldwide as a great artist, was also an outstanding engineer of the Renaissance period. He created drawings of technical devices, developed highly refined graphical representations of mechanical mechanisms, and advanced the methods of perspective and spatial representation.

Pafnuty Chebyshev (1821–1894) contributed significantly to the development of mechanism theory and graphical calculation methods. He developed methods for the graphical analysis of motion transmission mechanisms and played an important role in the advancement of mechanical engineering graphics.

Karl Culmann (1821–1881) is recognized as the founder of graphical statics. He developed methods for calculating construction structures through graphical approaches and made substantial contributions to engineering graphical calculation systems.

Ivan Sutherland (born 1938) is considered one of the pioneers of computer graphics. In 1963, he created the “Sketchpad” program, developed the foundations of interactive computer graphics, and laid the groundwork for the emergence of CAD systems. Modern automated design systems are largely based on his innovations.

John Walker (born 1949), the founder of Autodesk, was one of the main initiators in the creation of the AutoCAD software. He popularized CAD technologies, and his activities marked the beginning of the digital stage in the development of engineering graphics.

Eastern scholars also made invaluable contributions not only to the discipline under study, but to all exact sciences in general. Muhammad al-Khwarizmi (783–850) is universally recognized as the founder of algebra. He developed the theory of computational algorithms, which later became the foundation for the algorithmic principles of modern computer graphics.

Abu Rayhan al-Biruni (973–1048) contributed greatly to the development of geodesy and measurement sciences. He conducted research on spatial measurements and coordinate systems and laid the foundations for engineering measurement methods and the theory of graphical precision.

This discipline performs the following functions in education:

- develops spatial imagination;
- forms technical thinking;
- improves graphical literacy;
- develops practical skills in working with modern CAD (Computer-Aided Design) systems.

The main objectives of the subject “Engineering and Computer Graphics” are as follows:

- to develop students’ professional competencies in reading, creating, analyzing, and executing engineering drawings using modern automated design software;
- to develop graphical culture;
- to enhance engineering thinking;
- to strengthen spatial imagination;
- to master digital graphic technologies;
- to develop skills in automating the design process.

The tasks of the discipline can be classified into the following categories:

1. Theoretical Tasks:

- teaching the fundamentals of engineering graphics;
- explaining projection methods;
- mastering the elements of descriptive geometry;
- familiarizing students with standards (O’zDSt, GOST, ISO).

2. Practical Tasks:

- preparing drawings of parts and assemblies;
- teaching the rules of dimensioning;
- correctly representing sections and cross-sections;
- creating electronic drawings.

3. Formation of Digital Competencies:

- working with CAD systems;

- 2D and 3D modeling;
- editing and exporting drawings;
- preparing projects for printing and publication.

An Automated Design System (ADS) is a комплекс of software and technical tools that automates the processes of designing, modeling, and documenting technical objects through computer technologies. Its English equivalent is CAD (Computer-Aided Design).

The main objectives of ADS are:

- accelerating the design process;
- increasing accuracy;
- reducing errors;
- simplifying project modification and redesign;
- creating digital archives.

The main components of ADS include:

- software support (AutoCAD, SolidWorks, and others);
- technical support (computers, plotters, printers);
- information support (libraries, blocks, standards);
- methodological support (guidelines, standards).

The advantages of ADS are:

- saving time;
- improving drawing quality;
- providing opportunities for 3D modeling;
- enabling rapid project editing;
- integrating calculation processes.

General Information about the AutoCAD Graphic Program

The AutoCAD graphic program provides users with broad opportunities to fully realize their professional and creative ideas, allowing them to design objects in any desired form and structure. For this reason, millions of scientists, design engineers, specialists, students, and learners worldwide — more than 60 million users across over 80 countries and in 18 languages — have chosen the AutoCAD graphic system as an effective tool for performing design tasks. Consequently, AutoCAD is recognized as an international standard software for automated design activities. Therefore, the Autodesk company, the developer of the software, continuously improves and updates its new versions every year. Although the first version of AutoCAD was created in 1982, and more than four decades have passed since its introduction, it still remains one of the leading and most popular modern graphic programs. This is because the software is highly efficient, user-friendly, and capable of producing all types of schemes and drawings in both two-dimensional (2D) and three-dimensional (3D) formats with high precision and quality [8].

For this reason, specialists working on complex and highly detailed projects initially create such objects in the AutoCAD graphic program and later process them in 3D MAX or other graphic software to achieve a final visualization that closely resembles the real appearance of the object. In addition, the program provides the capability to convert drawings between two-dimensional (2D) and three-dimensional (3D) formats.

In the AutoCAD graphic program, graphical objects are created through a sequence of direct interactions between the specialist and the computer by using prepared command packages corresponding to graphical data elements and by entering the required dimensions.

The AutoCAD program is widely used by specialists in the following fields:

- Construction;
- Architecture;
- Mechanical engineering;
- Energy engineering;
- Land reclamation;
- Agriculture.

When selecting topics for practical classes in the subject "Engineering and Computer Graphics," it is advisable to begin by teaching students how to create basic drawing primitives on a computer. This approach is considered appropriate because, in educational didactics, the principle of moving from simple concepts to more complex ones is regarded as one of the most effective teaching methods. Indeed, students who master drawing commands and command algorithms in a computer environment are capable of creating objects of any level of complexity using this software.

It is well known that any graphical information consists of a set of points, segments, straight lines, polygons, circles, arcs, and curves created through various methods. This educational manual is aimed at developing students' practical skills and competencies in computer-based drawing by teaching them how to create and color these primitives, assign line types and thicknesses, generate connections based on circles, remove unnecessary lines, move and duplicate images, create symmetrical reflections, insert text, apply dimensions, edit completed drawings and written text, design objects in 3D format, create complex objects using specific commands, perform sections and cross-sections in three-dimensional images, observe objects from different spatial viewpoints, and apply continuous motion effects to visual representations [8].

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